

LOW REYNOLDS NUMBER EFFECTS ON HIGHLY LOADED COMPRESSOR STATOR CASCADE

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ABSTRACT

The performance of a highly loaded compressor stator is limited by increased viscous losses caused by operating at a low Reynolds number (Re). The numerical investigation has been carried out on a linear stator cascade profile with an inlet Mach number of 0.9. A test section has been designed based on the extracted streamlines from cascade simulations to perform an experimental investigation of Shock Wave Boundary Layer Interaction (SBLI). Three-dimensional simulations have been carried out on the test section model using a steady state RANS with EARSM turbulence model including transition effects. The low Re number 2.3×10^5 case has been investigated on test section configuration and is compared with the high Re number 7.3×10^5 case while maintaining the same Mach inflow conditions. A detailed comparison of boundary layer and SBLI investigations have been performed to analyze the different Reynolds number effects on a representative test section configuration.

KEYWORDS

Transonic Flows, SBLI, Linear Cascade, Low Reynolds Number, Turbomachinery, Internal Flows

NOMENCLATURE

AVDR	Axial Velocity Density Ratio	Ps	Static Pressure [Pa]
EARSM	Explicit Algebraic Reynolds Stress Model	Pt	Total Pressure [Pa]
IGG	Interactive Grid Generator	U	Mean Velocity [m/s]
LE	Leading Edge	τ_w	Wall Shear Stress [Pa]
RANS	Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes	δ	Boundary Layer thickness [mm]
Re	Reynolds Number	δ^*	Displacement thickness [mm]
RRD	Rolls Royce Deutschland	δ^{**}	Momentum thickness [mm]
SBLI	Shock wave Boundary Layer Interaction	ρ	Density [kg/m ³]
TE	Trailing Edge		
TSFC	Thrust Specific Fuel Consumption		
TFAST	Transition Location Effects on Shock Wave Boundary Layer Interaction		
C	Chord Length [mm]		
M	Mach Number		
H	Shape Factor		

INTRODUCTION

Modern aircraft engines with highly loaded transonic compressors have a great potential to minimize the weight and length of an axial compressor by reducing the number of compressor stages [1]. This leads to an increase in flow velocities relative to the blades with supersonic speeds and shock waves upstream and within the blade passages [2]. High-loading conditions caused by higher stage pressure ratios are vulnerable to losses, whereas compressor blades are more sensitive to the adverse pressure gradients caused by Shock Wave Boundary Layer Interaction (SBLI). These shock waves and SBLI act as additional sources of losses in highly loaded transonic compressors [3]. One of the major challenges faced in engines is at higher altitude conditions where the low Reynolds number (Re) effect plays a major role in the performance of a compressor. Under these conditions lower density causes higher kinematic viscosity resulting significant reduction of Reynolds number. At low Reynolds number conditions, the viscous losses dominate the flow which has a significant impact on the stability and operating range of the compressors [4].

The aerodynamic performance of turbomachinery blading is strongly dependent on the nature of the boundary layer developed on the surface of the profiles and its interaction with the flow field [5]. The nature of SBLI critically depends on the boundary layer conditions (laminar or turbulent) upstream of the shock interaction [6]. To minimize drag caused by skin friction, huge efforts were made with a variety of applications to keep the laminar boundary layer as long as possible upstream of the normal shock [7]. As a result of this advantage, the laminar boundary layer is chosen as a drag-reducing design choice for external flows and low Reynolds number (Re) operations at higher altitudes in internal flows. Laminar boundary layers have the benefit of reduced drag but are more vulnerable to separation in adverse pressure gradients. This can enhance total pressure losses and turbulence in internal flows [8]. Laminar boundary layer interaction with shock wave is more likely to have a separation, so the weaker shock can cause such an effect of interaction. Therefore laminar SBLI should be avoided, especially when this interaction becomes unstable resulting in shock oscillation in internal flows [9].

The laminar boundary layer is more liable to separate than the turbulent boundary layer on shock interaction. If laminar separation reaches to severe level rotating stall occurs in the blade passage resulting in the degradation of engine performance and aerodynamic stability [10]. At low Re number conditions, the shear layer is unconditionally unstable due to increased receptivity of freestream turbulence that excites the shear layer, resulting in quick transition and reattachment as a turbulent boundary layer [11]. The SBLI effects at different Reynolds conditions in turbomachinery applications have been investigated for decades but its detrimental effects on aerodynamic performance are still not completely understood. At low Reynolds conditions the transition from laminar to a turbulent boundary layer has a serious impact on the overall drag and performance of the blade [12]. Therefore the transition is delayed as much as possible to take advantage of the laminar boundary layer and to induce transition, flow control methods are deployed upstream of the shock interaction to avoid laminar SBLI. The boundary layer transition upstream of the shock wave has a positive effect on SBLI due to the interaction being turbulent SBLI resulting reduction of separation size, losses in the wake, and shock wave unsteadiness [13]. The 3-dimensional structure of the separation bubble and secondary flows due to end-wall effects at different Reynolds conditions are widely researched for axial compressors. Even though with present advancements in numerical tools it is still not able to predict accurately the mid-span boundary layer behavior in cascade flows due to the uncertainties in predicting 2D and 3D boundary layer behavior on airfoils, especially at end-walls interaction region where secondary flow separations are prominent [14].

GEOMETRY DESCRIPTION

To investigate the SBLI effects on highly loaded compressor stators profile at low Reynolds conditions an optimized representative linear stator cascade geometry [15] has been delivered by the TEAMAero project partner Rolls-Royce Deutschland Ltd & Co KG (RRD). For better optical access in test section measurement, the profile chord length has been up-scaled to chord 50 mm (scale factor of 1.72). The span-wise width has been defined as 100 mm due to the fixed definition of wind tunnel configuration giving a span-to-chord aspect ratio of 2. As a result of the increased chord length, the Reynolds number and secondary flows increase. The geometrical parameters of this cascade have been defined in Table 1.

Parameters	Units	Cascade
Inlet Mach Number	-	0.90
Chord Length	mm	50
Span-wise width	mm	100
Pitch	mm	30.35
Thickness	mm	2.75
Flow Inlet Angle	deg	48.14
Flow Exit Angle	deg	21.96
Stagger Angle	deg	30.31

Table 1: Stator Cascade Parameters

To investigate the SBLI effects experimentally a new rectilinear convergent test section model has been designed based on the experience from previous EU projects UFAST [16] and TFAST [17] for IMP-PAN transonic blow-down wind tunnel facility as shown in Figure 1. At the preliminary stage, the shape of the upper and lower walls of the test section has been designed based on the streamlines extracted from the cascade blade passage to have a similar shape of streamline. The main purpose of designing a test section is to reproduce a similar flow structure as in cascade simulation. One of the major challenges in designing a test section is to achieve the required inlet Mach number and inflow uniformity as per design criteria [18].

Figure 1: CAD model of designed test section

The relative location of profiles in the test section is defined as similar to a cascade arrangement and no incident effects are applied in the test section. The inlet convergent nozzles are shown in Figure 1 to help in achieving the required inlet Mach number of 0.9 as per requirement and flow periodicity upstream of the profiles. The benefit of such kind of approach is the freedom of profile translation in the test section without changing the inflow conditions [19]. The upper and lower profiles are mounted to the supporting structures and the middle profile is mounted on the sidewalls made of plexiglass.

A pair of suction slots have been defined on the upper and lower wall close to the blade passage to reduce the blockage effect on flow structure due to the development of boundary layers on upper and lower walls and corner flows. Since these suction slots are connected to the vacuum tank, the corner flow is controlled. Based on the effectiveness of the flow structure in the blade passages, the optimal location of the suction slots on the upper and lower wall has been determined. Additionally, these suction slots and perforated walls also help in achieving the required inflow conditions in the test section [20]. The number of blades in the test section was chosen to be three blades based on multiple aspects like test section configuration, experimental feasibility, etc. The suction and pressure side of the middle profile is the main focus of this research due to the end-wall effects reduced influence on flow structure when compared to the upper and lower profiles. All of the investigations are presented in this paper with a focus on the effects on the middle profile's suction side. The suction slot effect is not taken into consideration in the results presented in this paper. The preferred location of shock-wave on the suction side of the middle profile is achieved in the test section by adjusting the static pressure at the second throat of the test section channel outlet as shown in Figure 1.

NUMERICAL MODEL DESCRIPTION

The numerical computation has been performed using the commercial CFD tool from Numeca FINETM/Turbo specifically developed for turbomachinery applications. The numerical schemes from FINETM/Turbo solve steady-state 3D Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes equations (RANS) on a generally structured multi-block grid configuration. The structured mesh was generated using Numeca/AutoGrid5 for cascade configuration and Numeca/IGG (Interactive Geometry Modeler and Multi Block Structured Grid Generator) for test section configuration. The cascade mesh domain consists of 7 blocks with 7×10^6 cells. The test section geometry with mesh domain consists of 126 blocks with 24×10^6 cells as shown in Figure 2. The resolution of mesh close to the walls is kept adequate to obtain a y^+ of 1. Spatial discretization using a second-order central difference scheme with scalar artificial dissipation formulated by Jameson [21] was applied. The two-equation nonlinear eddy viscosity turbulence model of the Baseline Explicit Algebraic Reynolds Stress Model (BSL–EASRM) proposed by Menter [22], which is an extension of $k-\omega$ SST turbulence model as shown in (Equation 1 and 2).

$$\frac{D\rho k}{Dt} = \tau_{ij} \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} - \beta^* \rho \omega k + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[(\mu + \sigma_k \mu_t) \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \right] \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{D\rho \omega}{Dt} = \frac{\gamma}{\nu_t} \tau_{ij} \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} - \beta \rho \omega^2 + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[(\mu + \sigma_\omega \mu_t) \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x_j} \right] + 2\rho (1 - F_1) \sigma_{\omega 2} \frac{1}{\omega} \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x_j} \quad (2)$$

A generalized transition model proposed by Menter and Langtry [23] has been chosen. This model is based on two transport equations for the intermittency (γ) and for the transition momentum thickness Reynolds number ($\tilde{Re}_{\theta t}$) as shown in (Equation 3 and 4).

$$\frac{\partial \rho \gamma}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \rho u_j \gamma}{\partial x_j} = P_\gamma - E_\gamma + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_f} \right) \frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial x_j} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial \rho \tilde{R}e_{\theta t}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \rho u_j \tilde{R}e_{\theta t}}{\partial x_j} = P_{\theta t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\sigma_{\theta t} (\mu + \mu_t) \frac{\partial \tilde{R}e_{\theta t}}{\partial x_j} \right) \quad (4)$$

The perfect gas equation and Sutherland's law for viscosity complete the set of equations. A lot of investigations and research have shown that in RANS modeling the EARSM turbulence modeling could predict accurately the boundary layer separation at adverse pressure gradient and also secondary flows generated due to end-wall interaction with experiments [24],[25] and [26]. The boundary conditions have been defined in numerical simulations as per the requirements of the RRD. The inlet parameters in the test section have been defined with ambient total conditions (sea level) for high Reynolds conditions where as reduced inlet total pressure has been used based on the total pressure measured downstream of the inlet valve in the TFAST test section. The cascade simulations have been defined with periodic boundary conditions whereas, in the test section, these are replaced with end-walls with no-slip conditions. Also for the simulations performed the turbulence intensity has been defined as 4% as per the requirement from RRD.

Figure 2: Structured mesh and topology generated for test section configuration using Numeca/IGG

Mesh Convergence Study

The convergence study procedure was performed as described by Celik et al. [27]. Firstly, three meshes resolutions of roughly (332×145 , 280×101 and 196×85) cells (N) on the suction side of the middle blade keeping $y^+ = 1$ close to the wall were created, and the representative cell size was measured (h). Secondly, RANS simulations were performed with the numerical setup described in the next section. Finally, the local averaged static pressure at the suction side of the middle profile was picked as the critical variable (ϕ), and the discretization error was estimated. The results obtained are summarized in Table 2. From these results, the mid-refinement level shown in Figure 2 was chosen for the numerical investigation. This level provides the best balance between accuracy in predicting boundary layer effects in SBLI for test section simulations, with a GCI of 0.0866%, and calculation time within the scope of limits.

Parameters	Units	Values
N_1, N_2, N_3	-	48140, 28280, 16660
h_1, h_2, h_3	mm	0.3, 0.4, 0.5
ϕ_1, ϕ_2, ϕ_3	kPa	59360, 59327, 59157
r^{21}, r^{32}	-	1.3047, 1.3029
GCI^{21}, GCI^{32}	%	0.0166, 0.0866

Table 2: Mesh Convergence Study on Test Section Model

NUMERICAL RESULTS

The numerical results have been divided into two sections. The first part describes a comparative study between the cascade and test section at a high Reynolds number condition. The second section describes the comparison of flow structure between high and low Reynolds number conditions in the test section configuration. Based on the total pressure estimation from inlet valve measurements at the IMP-PAN test section the inlet boundary conditions have been defined for numerical simulations as shown in Table 3. The outlet static pressure value has been adjusted accordingly to obtain the required inlet Mach number 0.9.

Cases	Reynolds Number	Inlet Total Pressure	Outlet Static Pressure
High Reynolds	7.3×10^5	100 000 Pa	76 600 Pa
Low Reynolds	2.3×10^5	31 200 Pa	23 300 Pa

Table 3: Boundary conditions for respective Re case

Comparison of Cascade and Test section

The flow structure in the cascade is compared with the test section configuration to ensure the effectiveness of the test section design. The main objective of the test section is to reproduce a similar flow structure as in cascade configurations. One of the major design differences is the introduction of upper and lower walls with a no-slip condition in the test section compared with periodic boundary conditions in cascade configurations. This has a significant effect on the test section flow structure due to adverse effects caused by the boundary layer development at the end-walls. Therefore suction slots have been defined on the upper and lower walls in the test section to control the boundary layer and to reduce corner flow resulting incorrect pressure

distribution in the test section. This AFC helps in achieving the required inflow conditions in the test section. The numerical results presented in this paper do not take into account the effect of suction slots. As a first step, the inlet Mach number has been adjusted to 0.9 in both the cascade and test section by adjusting the outlet static pressure. The flow periodicity could be checked by plotting the Mach number on a traverse plotted one chord length upstream of the leading edge of the middle profile as shown in Figure 3a. The contour plot of the Mach number plotted at the mid-span location in the cascade and test section have been shown in Figure 3b. Since the inflow conditions are adjusted, the distribution of the shock on the middle profile has been plotted at the mid-span location using isentropic Mach number for cascade and test section as shown in Figure 3c. The shock wave is slightly stronger and shifted downstream on the suction and pressure side in the test section compared to the cascade configuration due to end-wall effects and different blade loading conditions. Also, these differences are justified based on AVDR (Axial Velocity Density Ratio) values shown in Table 4. The increased value of AVDR depicts larger secondary flows and a narrow flow field above the suction side of the middle profile. This results in flow acceleration and increased shock strength in the test section middle blade compared to the cascade configuration.

Figure 3: Comparison of cascade and test section, (a) Inlet Mach number plotted upstream leading edge, (b) Mach number contour plot, (c) Isentropic Mach number plotted on middle profile of cascade and test section

Comparison of Reynolds Number in Test section

Based on the comparison study performed in the cascade and test section at high Reynolds number conditions, we could conclude the design effectiveness of the test section in reproducing the similar flow structure as in cascade simulations. Therefore different Reynolds number effects with the same inlet Mach number of 0.9 are simulated and compared in the test section configuration. The boundary conditions for different Reynolds number conditions have been defined as shown in Table 3. To investigate the Reynolds number effect in representative test section configuration flow structure on the suction side of the middle profile has been compared.

To locate and visualize the shock wave and shock structure on the suction side of the middle profile numerical schlieren based on density gradient magnitude have been plotted as shown in Figure 4. Along with numerical schlieren isentropic Mach number and wall shear stress on the suction side of the middle profile have been plotted in Figure 4. The zero line of the shear stress shows the separation location where the flow gets separated due to the development of a separation bubble caused by SBLI and reattached downstream the shock resulting in huge separation based on the type of SBLI. The separation and reattachment lines plotted against the profile show the location and length of the separation bubble and it is evident that in the low Reynolds case, we have a large separation bubble that starts at $x/C=0.29$ and ends at $x/C=0.53$ whereas in high Reynolds it starts at $x/C=0.31$ and ends at $x/C=0.48$.

Figure 4: Numerical schlieren comparison of middle profile in test section with isentropic Mach number and wall shear stress plotted on suction side of middle profile

From numerical schlieren, it is visible that there is a strong shock on the suction and pressure side of the high Reynolds case compared to the low Reynolds case. And this is affirmed by the isentropic Mach number plot in Figure 4. The λ -foot is more clearly visible in the high Reynolds case where as there is a larger propagation of compression waves upstream the normal shock in low Reynolds condition due to a larger separation bubble generated at low Reynolds condition. It is also evident that large secondary shock structures are present downstream of the normal shock in the low Reynolds case which are very weak structures in the high Reynolds case. Due to the large separation bubble generated at low Reynolds condition the separation downstream of the shock and boundary layer thickening also gets larger compared to high Reynolds condition. To visualize the location and shape of the separation bubble and secondary flows on the suction and pressure side of the middle profile iso-surface of the axial velocity component have been plotted and depicted as blue color in Figure 5a.

Figure 5: (a) Traverse location for calculating AVDR, (b) Comparison of flow structure at middle profile in test section

These plots affirm the conclusions from Figure 4. The secondary flows due to the side wall effect are also marked as corner flows in Figure 5a. To estimate the size of secondary flows in blade passage, AVDR has been calculated based on (Equation 5).

$$AVDR = (\rho_2 w_2 \sin \beta_2) / (\rho_1 w_1 \sin \beta_1) \quad (5)$$

The mass averaged axial velocity component and density have been extracted from the traverse located at 10% of chord length upstream and downstream the middle blade to calculate AVDR are shown in Figure 5b. Based on this estimation the AVDR has been estimated for the test section and cascade for high and low Reynolds conditions.

Reynolds Number Case	AVDR
Test Section High Re	1.147
Test Section Low Re	1.099
Cascade High Re	1.129

Table 4: AVDR for test section and cascade for different Reynolds number conditions

Based on the estimation from AVDR shown in Table 4, It is visible that there are larger secondary flows in the high Reynolds condition for the test section and cascade compared to the low Reynolds condition. AVDR parameters have a strong influence on blade pressure distribution and blade performance [28]. Therefore, the difference in the isentropic Mach number plot in Figure 3c is an effect of higher AVDR in the test section. It is crucial to determine the boundary layer parameters while investigating the effects at different Re number conditions. Velocity profiles have been compared at different locations from the leading edge to the trailing edge. Two traverses (1-2) upstream of the shock, one traverse (3) at the separation bubble, and two traverses downstream of the shock foot (4-5) have been plotted and shown in Figure 6. At traverse 1 we could see attached laminar boundary layer for both Reynolds number cases and there is a slightly higher acceleration in the high Reynolds number case.

Figure 6: Comparison of velocity profiles plotted at selected traverse location on suction side of middle profile

Figure 7: Comparison of thickness and integral parameters of boundary layer plotted at 9 traverse along the suction side of middle profile from leading edge to trailing edge

At traverse 2, the high Reynolds case is still similar to traverse 1 but for the low Reynolds case it is already in a separation bubble and a zone of reversed flow represents the velocity. Traverse 3 shows the separation bubble and the velocity profile shows the size of the separation bubble at that location. Traverse 4 and 5 show the typical turbulent shape of the velocity profile close to the wall and shows a transitional behavior further away from the wall. A comparison study for all integral parameters of the boundary layer has been plotted at 9 traverses from the leading edge to the trailing edge on the suction side of the middle profile in the test section as shown in Figure 7. In the entire suction side of the middle profile, the boundary layer thickness in the low Reynolds number case is greater than in the high Reynolds number case. From Figure 7 till 30% of the chord, we could see that the boundary layer thickness is too thin and the shape factor also affirms that the boundary layer is laminar in the state. Conventionally, $H=2.59$ Blasius boundary layer [29] is typical of laminar flows, while $H=1.3$ to 1.4 is typical of turbulent flows. At $x/C=0.3$, strong shock-induced boundary layer separation with reattachment is characterized by the significant rise in shape factor in the interaction zone and the steep decrease further downstream [30]. The reattachment in the high Reynolds case is at $x/C=0.5$ whereas in low Reynolds it is at $x/C=0.6$. For both Reynolds cases, one could observe an increase in boundary layer thickness downstream of the shock wave, however, for the low Reynolds case, the difference between the high Reynolds case is significant. Downstream the shock foot the boundary layer thickness increases which translates the amount of losses. As a result of the effect of shock wave interaction with the laminar boundary layer, which results in a large separation bubble and flow separation downstream of the bubble, losses are substantially higher in the low Reynolds situation.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper discusses the numerical investigation carried out in the transonic compressor cascade defined by RRD. A test section has been designed based on the streamlines extracted from the cascade simulation with the objective to reproduce the flow structure on the suction side of stator in cascade configuration. The numerical investigation of Reynolds number effect has been carried out on the middle profile in the test section and compared with cascade simulations. It is shown that the design objective is achieved and the flow structure as well as distribution of flow quantities in the test section are similar in cascade, in spite of limited space and number of profiles in the test section. The shock wave boundary layer interaction on suction side leads to the boundary layer separation. In case of low Reynolds number, the separation zone is larger than for high Reynolds number. Although, the numerical simulations show comparable thickness of boundary layer upstream of the shock wave, the difference in the interaction zone is significant. As the effect, the boundary layer differs downstream of the shock wave for both cases and the wake is thicker for low Reynolds case than for high Reynolds. As a next step, the test section will be assembled at the IMP PAN transonic wind tunnel and detailed measurements for various flow conditions will be carried out to evaluate Reynolds effect.

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